

Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean

M6.3 First Draft of the Atlas of Maps

VERSION 1

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Authors	Ioanna Anyfanti, Antonis Lyronis			
Reviewer(s)	George Karatzas, Emmanouil Varouchakis Janire Uribe-Asarta, Vanessa A. Godoy, J. Jaime Gómez-Hernández			

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Executive Summary

The overall objective of the InTheMED project is to implement innovative and sustainable management tools and remediation strategies for MED aquifers (inland and coastal) in order to mitigate anthropogenic and climate-change threats by creating new long-lasting spaces of social learning among different interdependent stakeholders, NGOs, and scientific researchers in five field case studies. These are located at the two shores of the MED basin, namely in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Tunisia, and Turkey.

InTheMED will develop an inclusive process that will establish an ensemble of innovative assessment and management tools and methodologies including a high-resolution monitoring approach, smart modelling, a socio-economic assessment, web-based decision support systems (DSS) and new configurations for governance to validate efficient and sustainable integrated groundwater management in the MED considering both the quantitative and qualitative aspects.

This milestone, namely M6.3, is part of Task 6.3 “Production of Maps from the DSS Tool According to Suggested Scenarios and Dissemination with Stakeholders” (Lead TUC, participants: UPV, UFZ, IST-ID, CERTE and BU). The aim of M6.3 is to give a short description of the way the results of the DSS are spatially represented.

1. Graphical User Interface as a DSS tool

A Graphical User Interface (GUI) application has been developed, which unifies the whole set of case studies. The user can set the input parameters and run the desired model for a specific case study. The results are spatially represented data (maps) that are also extracted as .kml files and can be previewed in Google Earth geobrowser. A comparison option between two different scenarios for the same case study site, in one split screen, will also be provided.

A framework for the Konya study area has been developed through the artificial neural-network-based surrogate model built for Task 3.2: “Training and validation of the models in the case studies” (Todaro et al., 2023). The precipitation coefficient, the water crop demand coefficient and the period of simulation constitute the input parameters set of the current model (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Graphical User Interface - inputs

A sample output for the current framework is presented in Figures 2 and 3.

Figure 2. Output of a Surrogate Model run for Konya study area

Figure 3. Spatially represented output data in Google Earth - .kml file

Equivalently, a space-time ordinary kriging geostatistical method has been developed as a surrogate model for the Tympaki study area. The framework accepts as inputs the groundwater level, the pumping rate and the period of the desired simulation. The maps and the .kml files are produced in the exact way. Furthermore, a Random Forest-based framework for the Requena-Utiel study area has also been developed within WP3. The two models mentioned above are currently being integrated into the executable GUI, in such a manner that a complete decision support system (DSS) will be developed. The DSS is intended to be deployed on a web server to offer a complete web-based tool to validate efficient and sustainable integrated groundwater management in the MED. A summary of the progress on the DSS tool development is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of the progress on the DSS tool development

Surrogate model for	Availability	Integration in the GUI
Requena-Utiel (Spain)	Yes	In Progress
Tympaki (Greece)	Yes	In Progress
Castro Verde (Portugal)	Yes	
Grombalia (Tunisia)	Yes	
Konya (Turkey)	Yes	In Progress

2. References

Todaro, Valeria, Secci, Daniele, D'Oria, Marco, Tanda, Maria Giovanna, & Zanini, Andrea. (2023). InTheMed D3.2 Report on Surrogate Models in the Case Studies (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7674923>